

Supplementary materials:

Activation of brain-heart axis during REM sleep: a trigger for dreaming

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Questionnaire

Subject _____

Awakening number _____

Date _____ Night _____ Time _____

Sleep stage _____

1) What was the last thing that was going through your mind before the alarm (=last experience)?

No report

Something, but I can't remember what

Report

2) Were you awake or were you asleep? Awake Asleep

3) How far back in time can you remember about the experience you had? _____

4) On a scale of 1 to 5, how much was the experience perception instead of thought?

1 2 3 4 5

(1 = more thought than perception / 5 = more perception than thought)

5) On a scale of 1 to 5, how aware were you that the dream experience wasn't real?

1 2 3 4 5

(1 = not aware at all / 5 very aware)

6) On a scale of 1 to 5, how much were you in control of the content of your dream?

1 2 3 4 5

(1 = nessun controllo / 5 = molto controllo)

7) On a scale of 1 to 5, how much was the experience centered on yourself instead of the environment you were in?

1 2 3 4 5

(1 = on the environment I was in / 5 = on myself)

8) On a scale of 1 to 5, how much was the experience associated with:

a. Visual content: 1 2 3 4 5

b. Tactile content: 1 2 3 4 5

c. Auditory content: 1 2 3 4 5

d. Olfactory content: 1 2 3 4 5

e. Gustatory content: 1 2 3 4 5

f. Emotional content: 1 2 3 4 5 → Positive Negative

9) The experience took place in a...
Closed environment External environment Neither

10) Were there other individuals besides yourself?

Only me Only others Both me and others

11) Did you perceive any faces? Yes No Maybe

12) Were there any moving elements? Yes No Maybe

→ Subjective movement External movement